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ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

Estrategias para motivar a los estudiantes a participar en actividades académicas y educativas complementarias para mejorar sus competencias

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Resumen

Este estudio explora el nexo entre la participación de los estudiantes universitarios en actividades académicas y extracurriculares y el desarrollo de sus habilidades de pensamiento crítico. Investiga la posible correlación entre la participación de los estudiantes en actividades extracurriculares y su competencia en los esfuerzos de equipo colaborativo dentro del entorno universitario. Además, la investigación busca determinar si existe un vínculo entre la participación académica y la finalización puntual de los programas de pregrado. El artículo también profundiza en la aplicación de las teorías del compromiso estudiantil en la educación superior para comprender estas relaciones, haciendo referencias comparativas al marco educativo en los Estados Unidos.

Palabras clave: educación, gestión, contexto sociocultural, gestión de la innovación, sistema.

Abstract

Strategies for motivating students to participate in academic and additional educational activities to improve their competencies

This study explores the nexus between university students' engagement in academic and extracurricular activities and their critical thinking skill development. It probes into the potential correlation between students' involvement in extracurricular engagements and their proficiency in collaborative team efforts within the university setting. Furthermore, the investigation seeks to determine if there is a link between academic involvement and the punctual completion of undergraduate programs. The article also delves into the application of student engagement theories in higher education to understand these relationships, making comparative references to the educational framework in the United States.

Keywords: education, management, sociocultural context, managing innovation, system.

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1. Introduction

In today's fast-paced society, it is crucial to educate professionals who are competitive, adaptable and innovative. Higher education is at the forefront of this challenge, tasked not just with imparting knowledge, but also with improving the competencies people need to thrive in today's environment.

Today's students are active participants in their educational journeys, influencing the trajectory and outcomes of their studies. Thus, the involvement of students in both academic and extracurricular activities is increasingly recognized as a vital goal of higher education institutions. Such engagement helps unlock student potential, developing core skills such as critical thinking, creative problem solving, independent learning, and effective teamwork that are key to professional success.

This research paper examines the complex mechanisms that link student engagement to competency development. He carefully studies theoretical foundations, evaluates current research results and offers practical ideas for educational institutions and their faculties.

Outside of the classroom, student involvement spans the spectrum of activities, from project participation to academic research, from participation in student government to attendance at cultural and sporting events. This broad scope recognizes that learning extends to all aspects of life, shaping intelligence, character and social engagement.

Although a significant body of research, particularly research focusing on American college students, suggests a beneficial relationship between student engagement and skill development and academic achievement, this relationship is not universally observed. Notably, studies in different educational landscapes, such as Taiwan and Korea, show mixed results. In some cases, there is no clear correlation between student

engagement and academic performance, highlighting the complexities associated with different cultural and pedagogical frameworks.

Predominant research, mostly centered around American academia, supports the notion that active student engagement correlates with both skill acquisition (as noted by Strauss and Terenzini, 2007; Roulin and Bangerter, 2013; Kilgo et al., 2015) and academic progress (Kuh). et al., 2008; Wang & Degol, 2014; Fredricks, J. A., Filsecker, M., & Lawson, M. A., 2016). However, counterpoints arise in the international context. For example, Hsieh (2014) studied Taiwanese university students and found no significant relationship between level of engagement and academic grades, even after accounting for demographic differences, socioeconomic background, and individual motivation. Similarly, a study of Korean students (Choi, Rhee, 2014) found that their educational experiences and outcomes differed significantly from those of their peers around the world, suggesting that the effectiveness of student engagement may be mediated by distinctive cultural and educational experiences.

2. Materials and methods

The uniqueness of this study lies in several important aspects:

Innovative Systematic Approach: This study marks a pioneering attempt to systematically examine how different aspects of student engagement, including both classroom and extracurricular activities, affect educational achievement. This is the first study of its kind to comprehensively examine these elements in tandem, providing a new perspective on student engagement in educational institutions.

Methodological advantage: Unlike previous studies in this area, which were mostly conducted outside this context, this study boasts significant methodological improvements. Through the use of a variety of data collection tools—from student self-reports and standardized tests to detailed administrative records and in-depth student interviews—the study offers a richer, more detailed, and more objective understanding of learning outcomes. This multidimensional approach surpasses traditional research methods, allowing for a more detailed and accurate representation of the educational landscape.

Expanding Education: The findings of this study aim to significantly expand our understanding of the dynamics between student engagement and academic success. By shedding light on this relationship, the study provides valuable information for higher education institutions and education policy makers. The knowledge gained can contribute to the development of more effective educational programs and strategies aimed not only at improving the learning experience, but also at increasing the overall level of education. The implications of this research go beyond simple academic achievement, potentially influencing the future direction of educational practice and policy.

3. Results

Research consistently demonstrates a significant positive relationship between students' level of engagement and their academic achievement, particularly in terms of grades (Kuh et al., 2008). The research by Kuh and his colleagues highlights the key role that student engagement plays in the success of a bachelor's degree. This achievement is not just a personal milestone; this has far-reaching consequences, contributing to long-term social and economic improvement. These benefits are not limited to individuals or their immediate family, but extend to society as a whole, increasing the overall quality of life (Kuh et al., 2008).

Further research examines the effects of specific types of student engagement. For example, active participation in collaborative projects and interactions with peers from different cultures are associated with significant improvements in critical thinking skills (Tsui, 2008; Kim, J. & Bastedo, M.N., 2016). Special attention is also paid to the dynamics of interaction between teachers and students. These interactions often extend beyond the normal classroom environment to include faculty-led research initiatives and practical application projects. Such engagements are critical to developing students' independent thinking abilities and improving their skills in synthesizing and evaluating diverse ideas (Hand et al., 2011; Kilgo et al., 2015).

As a result, student engagement is closely related not only to skill acquisition, but also to timely completion of educational programs. This correlation has led to an increase in the popularity of surveys in educational institutions, particularly in the United States, Canada, and Australia. These surveys aim to collect detailed information about the nature and frequency of student activities, both in academic and extracurricular areas. They aim to understand how students perceive and engage with the various educational and extracurricular opportunities offered by universities (Pascarella et al., 2010; Johnstone et al., 2018; Douglas, J. A., Thomson, G. & Zhao, K.-M., 2012). This growing body of research not only sheds light on effective teaching methods, but also helps develop strategies to improve the overall educational experience and outcomes for students.

The principles of student involvement in modern pedagogy cover several key dimensions:

Holistic engagement: Student engagement is recognized as a complex commitment involving both time and cognitive effort in academic activities. The theory states that the more time and intellectual energy students invest in learning activities, the more favorable the results will be.

Dynamic Engagement: The concept of student engagement is dynamic in nature. This implies different levels of involvement of different students in certain activities or events, as well as fluctuations in the involvement of the same student in different types of activities.

Measurable Aspects of Engagement: Engagement can be quantified in terms of both quantity (e.g., hours spent preparing for class) and quality (e.g., depth of understanding vs. rote memorization).

Direct Correlation with Development: There is a direct correlation between students' academic effort and their skill development and personal growth.

Key findings and implications include:

Academic Participation and Critical Thinking: Active participation in academic activities, such as engaging in discussions and applying interdisciplinary knowledge, is positively correlated with enhanced critical thinking skills.

Extracurricular Activities and Teamwork: Participating in extracurricular activities such as student organizations is beneficial for developing teamwork and critical thinking skills.

Withdrawal and on-time program completion: Failure to meet academic requirements creates a significant barrier to completing university programs on schedule.

Cultural Differences in Engagement: The pattern of academic engagement among American students differs from that of other countries, with American students spending more time on classes and assignments. The impact of extracurricular activities on academic performance is less pronounced in comparison.

4. Discussion

These principles emphasize the multifaceted nature of student engagement and its critical role in shaping educational experiences and outcomes. They also emphasize the need to consider cultural and contextual differences when examining the impact of student engagement.

This study represents a pioneering systematic investigation of the relationship between student engagement and learning outcomes in higher education. It highlights the limitations of engagement theory, particularly in educational contexts with rigid academic structures and limited opportunities for engagement. The study points to the need for a balanced approach to structuring the educational experience and organizing new student initiatives to improve educational outcomes. The conclusions are especially relevant for such regions as modern Ukraine, where discussions are ongoing regarding the improvement of student learning outcomes. This knowledge can guide the development of student curricula, the distribution of teaching load, and the planning of new student initiatives, providing universities with a framework to optimize the educational experience for students.

Based on the results of the research, the following proposals can be formulated that may be useful for universities:

Developing Critical Thinking and Teamwork: Engaging students in university-based extracurricular activities can help develop their critical thinking and teamwork skills. To do this, you can take the following measures:

Redistribution of students' academic load and expansion of educational formats that include extracurricular work of students, for example, within student organizations or project activities.

Creation of accessible platforms and open formats of extracurricular activities on the basis of the university, as well as creation of a department that coordinates extracurricular activities of students.

Expanding the practice of accounting for extracurricular achievements (for example, holding conferences/festivals, implementing charitable projects, etc.) in special scholarships and university incentives.

Completion of the Educational Program on Time: To increase the number of students who complete the educational program according to the established schedule, the following measures can be taken:

Monitoring student engagement (attendance, completed assignments) at the institutional level and providing targeted assistance to at-risk students, such as referrals for counseling and face-to-face meetings.

Conducting support courses for students who cannot learn the educational material.

Placement of first-year students in dormitories located close to academic buildings to reduce travel time. This will allow them to spend more time at the university and participate in extracurricular activities.

These proposals can serve as a basis for further research and implementation in the practice of universities with the aim of improving the educational results of students and facilitating their successful completion of the educational program.

5. Conclusion

Based on the basic ideas of the research, additional considerations and consequences become apparent, which further emphasizes the multifaceted nature of student involvement in higher education:

Developing personalized learning pathways: Universities should consider implementing personalized learning pathways that cater to individual student interests and career aspirations. This approach can significantly increase engagement by aligning learning content with students' personal and professional goals, thereby increasing motivation and relevance.

Integrating technology and innovative teaching methods: Incorporating technology and innovative pedagogical techniques can play a critical role in increasing student engagement. This includes online learning platforms, interactive software and virtual

reality experiences that can bring course material to life and engage a generation of digitally native students.

Creating an enabling learning environment: Creating an enabling and inclusive learning environment is key. This includes providing mental health support, mentoring programs, and fostering a campus culture that values diversity and inclusion. Such an environment not only promotes student retention, but also encourages active participation in both academic and extracurricular activities.

Emphasis on developing soft communication skills: In addition to academic competencies, soft communication skills such as communication, leadership and emotional intelligence are increasingly important in the professional world. Encouraging students to develop these skills through group projects, leadership roles in clubs, and other interactive activities can be very helpful.

Building Industry and Community Links: Establishing stronger links with industry and community organizations can provide students with hands-on experience and networking opportunities. Internships, community service and joint projects with businesses and local organizations can greatly enhance real-world learning and engagement.

Continuous assessment and feedback: Implementing continuous assessment and feedback systems can help monitor and enhance student engagement. Regular feedback allows for timely intervention and adjustment of instructional strategies, ensuring that the educational experience remains dynamic and responsive to student needs.

Global and Cross-Cultural Exposure: Offering opportunities for global exposure, such as study abroad programs and international collaborations, can broaden students' perspectives and understandings, enhance their educational experiences, and prepare them for the global workforce.

Research and Policy Implications: The findings of this study have significant implications for educational research and policy making. They call for policies that support diverse learning methods, encourage innovative teaching practices, and promote the well-rounded development of students.

In conclusion, this study not only highlights the importance of student engagement in improving learning outcomes, but also serves as a call to action for institutions to adopt more holistic, flexible and student-centred approaches in higher education. This underscores the need for constant evolution and adaptation in educational practices to meet the diverse needs and aspirations of today's students.

Data availability statement

The data and materials used in the work available for access.

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